

TRISIKLIK 1H-1,2,3-TRIAZOL HOSILALARINING SINTEZI**Z. I. Murtazayeva –**

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1,2,3-Triazol halqasi saqlagan geterosiklik birikmalar tibbiy kimyoda o‘zining strukturaviy tuzilishi va xilma-xil biologik faolliklari bilan muhim ahamiyatga ega hisoblanadi. Besh a‘zoli geterosiklik birikmalar orasida uchta azotli geteroatomga ega bo‘lgan triazol birlamchi geterosiklik molekula bo‘lib, birinchi marta 1885-yilda Bladdin tomonidan kashf etilgan. Ikkita π bog‘i va elektron jufti tufayli u aromatik xususiyatga ega [1]. Metabolik degradatsiyaga, kislota-asos gidroliziga va qaytarilish-oksizlanishga chidamliligi uning aromatiklik xususiyatining natijasidir [2]. 1,2,3-Triazol halqasini o‘z ichiga olgan gibrid birikmalar va tegishli geterosikllarning yetakchi birikmalari tibbiy kimyo sohasida saratonga qarshi, mikroblarga qarshi, silga qarshi, virusga qarshi, diabetga qarshi, bezgakka qarshi, leyshmaniyaga qarshi agentlar/nomzod birikmalar va neyroprotektiv vositalar yetarlicha topilgan [3-10] (1-rasm).

Tarkibida ekzosiklik aminoguruh saqlagan 1,2,3-triazollarning sintezi va kimyoviy xossalarini o‘rganish so‘nggi yillarda rivojlanib bormoqda. Buning asosiy sabablaridan biri aminoguruh yuqori reaksiya qobiliyatiga ega bo‘lib, uning asosida turli elektrofil almashinish (alkillash, asillash va b.) reaksiyalarini o‘rganish orqali turli yangi hosilalar olish mumkinligi, hamda yangi geteroxalqalar hosil qilish orqali potensial farmakologik moddalar sintez qilish mumkin.

Bizning tadqiqot guruhimiz etil sanoatsetat va bir necha xil fenil azidlar o‘rtasidagi 1,3-dipolyar sikllanish reaksiyasi orqali 1H-1,2,3-triazollarning yangi hosilalarini sintez qildi va va ularning strukturaviy tahlillarini o‘rgandi.

1-rasm. 1H-1,2,3-triazollar asosidagi dori vositalari

5-Amino-1-N-aril-1H-1,2,3-triazol etil efirlarining sintezini amalga oshirish uchun dastlabki modda sifatida anilin (**1a**), toluidin (**1b**) va 4-almashgan anilinlar (**1c-j**) tanlab olindi. Dastlab, anilin va uning hosilalari bilan natriy azidi, natriy nitrit hamda xlorid kislotasi ishtirokida 0-5 °C da 4 soat davomida xona haroratida magnit aralashtirgich yordamida aromatik elektrofil almashish reaksiyasi olib borildi. Olingan aril azidlar (**2a-j**) etil sianotsetat bilan natriy etoksid ishtirokida xona haroratidan 40 °C gacha bo'lgan sharoitda inert atmosferada uch soat davomida aralashtirildi. Reaksiya aralashmasi 50 ml muzli suvga quyildi. Olingan hosil bo'lgan kristallar filtrlash orqali yig'iladi va mos ravishda triazol efirlari (**3a-j**) 56 dan 93% gacha bo'lgan yaxshi unum bilan hosil bo'ldi (2-rasm).

2-rasm. 5-Amino-1-N-aril-1H-1,2,3-triazol etil efirlarining umumiy sintezi

1-Jadval. Yangi 5-amino-1-N-aril-1H-1,2,3-triazol etil efirlarining suyuqlanish harorati va hosil bo'lish unumlari:

R	Moddalar	Unumlar, %	Suyuqlanish harorati, °C
4-H	3a	62	130-131

4-Me	3b	65	154-155
4-Et	3c	67	159-160
4-F	3d	60	130–131
4-Cl	3e	95	157–159
4-Br	3f	93	164–165
4-OMe	3g	90	145–146
4-CF ₃	3h	91	148–149
3,4-Cl	3i	82	128–130
4-CN	3j	75	140–141

Reaksiyaning ikkinchi bosqichi 5-amino-1-*N*-aril-1*N*-1,2,3-triazol etil efirlari (**3a-j**) va 2-pirolidon (4) ning turli sharoitlarda POCl₃ ishtirokida reaksiya sharoitlarini optimallashtirish orqali olib borildi va siklizatsiya mahsuloti bo'lgan 1,2,3-triazollarning yangi trisiklik hosilalari (**5a-j**) sintez qilindi (3-rasm).

3-rasm. Yangi 1*H*-1,2,3-trisiklik triazol hosilalari sintezining umumiy sxemasi

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